

Gesture and Their Meaning of Artistic Movements in Welcoming Guest in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the gestures and meanings embedded in traditional regional dances of Indonesia, particularly those associated with welcoming guests. Recognizing the diminishing interest in these cultural practices among the younger generation. The study aims to provide insights into the significance of movements in dances from various Indonesian regions. The analysis draws on semiotic theory (Charles Sanders Peirce, 1857-1914), categorizing dance gestures into iconic, deictic, metaphoric, and beat forms. The researcher are interested in exploring gesture and their meaning of artistic movements in welcoming guest in Indonesia. Examining 10 regional dance videos, the researchers found that iconic gestures, visually depicting objects or concepts, dominate the welcoming dances, comprising 48% of the observed movements. Metaphoric gestures, conveying abstract concepts, follow at 32%, while deictic gestures, pointing to specific objects or people, constitute 12%. Beat gestures, synchronized with the rhythm of music or dance, account for 8%. This study contributes to preserving and understanding the cultural richness encapsulated in the gestures of traditional Indonesian dances, emphasizing the need to safeguard this heritage for future generations

INTRODUCTION

The ancestors of the archipelago in the past stated "dance, then I will know where you come from" because behind the presence of dance art is revealed the philosophy of culture and contained the mindset that underlies the culture of the creator and owner of the art. (Yakobus Sumardjo, 2003: 2). Gesture or movement in Indonesian regional dance has a deep meaning. Each dance movement contains a certain message, story, or expression.

According to Soedarsono (1984:3), dance is an expression of the human soul that is poured through rhythmic and beautiful movements. Which is poured through rhythmic and beautiful movements. Dance is a movement that is formed expressively created by humans to be enjoyed and felt. From this theory, that gestures and food in traditional dance from Indonesian regions are related to one another and cannot be separated. Gesture and meaning of regional dance from Indonesia, is one of the important aspects in a regional dance. Gestures in traditional dance refer to the body, hand, facial movements and expressions used in dance performances. These gestures have symbolic meanings and can tell stories, legends or cultural values. Each movement in traditional dance can have a specific meaning, such as honor, happiness, or a story about the daily life of the people who live it.

The meaning in traditional dance varies greatly based on the culture, region, and type of dance performed. Traditional dance is often used as a means to convey messages, commemorate important events, or express the feelings and historical stories of a particular community. Unfortunately, in this day and age, the correct understanding and practice of these dances has begun to fade because the younger generation is increasingly uninterested and less connected to these traditions. According to Hidigardis M. I. Nahuk (2019:65-76) states that: One of the factors that causes local culture to be forgotten nowadays is; the lack of the next generation who have an interest in learning and inheriting their own culture. This is the background of this research, to review and analyze the extent of the movements and meanings of traditional regional dances.

Various studies and analysis have indeed been carried out on the problem of preserving traditional regional dance in Indonesian example is about the international news. But there are still few who mention and connect with the gestures and meanings of traditional Indonesian dance. Of course, research like this needs to be done in order to provide information on how the gestures and meanings of a dance with its development and current problems. The results of this study also aim to determine the extent to which the interest of the younger generation today wants to know and learn traditional dance in Indonesia and provide information about the gestures and meanings of traditional Indonesian dance. Here is the preliminary data:

Figure 1. Saman Dance (Aceh)

In this picture, "Salam alaikum kami ucapkan, Para undangan yang baru teuka, Karena salam nabi keusunah jaro tamumat syarat mulia." ("Salam alaikum we say, newly arrived guests, since the greeting of the accursed prophet with the hand of accepting noble conditions.")

This movement signifies the presence of guests at that place, as well as the movement where the left hand is up, the right hand is right in front of the cheek, and the face looks to the side, is a gesture of movement which welcomes guests who are present, this is a regional dance from the Gayo highlands of Aceh province which originated from their ancestors, and it has been around for a long time, and has been passed down from generation to generation. This dance reflects education, religion, manners, heroism, cohesiveness and togetherness, this dance is usually used to welcome guests who are present. The dance movement above is a movement that goes into iconic gestures, because the movement gives a symbol that has meaning. the picture shows the dancers putting their hands together and placed in front of their chest while kneeling, this means that the dancers welcome the guests who come with respect and happiness.

Based on the explanation above, that gesture and meaning exist in regional dances in Indonesia where every movement in the dance has its meaning. and can be witnessed directly by the audience or invites present. The following are some related studies on gesture and meaning in regional welcoming dance in Indonesia:

1. Mais Yasen and Shaidah Jusoh. 2019. A systematic review on hand gesture recognition techniques, challenges and applications.
2. Purba, Nurhasanah, & Mulyanti. 2020. Gesture Meaning of Tortor used in Simalungun Wedding Ceremony.
3. Tarigan, Fatin Nadifa. 2021. Comparasion of Western and Indonesian Gestures in Communication: Sociolinguistics Study.
4. Kensy Cooperrider, Kate Mesh. 2022. Pointing in gesture and sign.
5. Fauziah Khairani

Lubis & Syamsul Bahri. 2023. Gestures and Their Meanings of Main Character in Daniel's Movie Everything Everywhere All at Once.

This research study differs in its specific focus on uncovering the underlying meanings embedded in the gestures and movements used in welcoming guest. It's concerning that a significant part of these culturally rich subtleties often escapes the notice of the audience. Consequently, the researchers aim to address this lack of awareness by shining a light on the shared elements present in these gestures and movements. The goal is to provide a thorough examination of the cultural components linked to welcoming guests in Indonesia, particularly emphasizing the frequently neglected nuances and commonalities in non-verbal expressions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Basically, semiotics is the study of the meaning of signs, including the myths and metaphors associated with them. The science of semiotics is that everything that can be observed or made observable can be called a sign. And signs are not limited to objects (Zoest, 1993:18). And According to Tinarbuko (2008), semiotics is the study of signs in order to know how they function and produce meaning. Meanwhile, according to Christomy and Yuwono (2004), semiotics is the study of signs, sign functions, and sign production. Basically, modern semiotic theory is divided into three, namely iconic, deictic, and metaphoric, which were first coined by the father of modern semiotics Charles Sanders Peirce in 1857 to 1914. But with the times the theory developed and became 4 parts including iconic, deictic, metaphoric, beat.

1. Iconic

Iconic gestures are body or hand movements that are used to visually depict certain objects, concepts or messages. Iconic is an adjective that refers to something that properties or characteristics that are highly recognized and identified by many people. It can refer to something that is a highly recognizable symbol or representation of a particular concept, culture, or event. Refers to the use of body movements and facial expressions that describe or illustrate a particular story or concept. Iconic movements are used to communicate ideas, emotions, or stories to the audience without words, this can include movements that symbolize warm welcome, happiness, and the natural or cultural beauty of the area.

Examples:

- a. A hand mimicking the flight of a bird to symbolize freedom or liberation.
- b. Cupping hands together to represent holding something precious, conveying care or protection.
- c. Outstretched arms imitating the shape of a mountain to signify strength and stability.
- d. Rotating the wrist in a circular motion to depict the turning of a key, symbolizing unlocking or discovery.

2. Deictic

Deictic gestures refer to body movements or physical cues used in communication to point to or refer to a specific object, person, place or time in an ongoing context. Deictic gestures help to give meaning to the object or person being pointed to or referred to in the communication situation. Deictic gestures are body or hand movements used to point or refer to objects, people, places, or elements. Deictic gesture aims to communicate a story or message without using words. A form of physical expression that facilitates understanding of what is being told.

Examples:

- a. Pointing directly to the side to indicate a specific location or direction.
- b. Nodding towards a person to acknowledge their presence or agreement.
- c. Gesturing toward an object on the table to draw attention to it in a conversation.
- d. Using the index finger to trace a route on a map, guiding someone through directions.

3. Metaphoric

Metaphoric gesture is a type of non-verbal gesture that uses movement or facial expression to describe or communicate a concept or message that is metaphorical in nature. Metaphoric gesture refers to the use of body movement or facial expression to describe or convey a message or concept that is metaphorical, symbolic, or abstract in nature. It is a way for dancers to convey deeper meanings or more complex concepts through movement.

Examples:

- a. Crossing arms over the chest to metaphorically convey a defensive or guarded attitude.
- b. Extending hands outward with palms up, symbolizing openness or receptivity.
- c. Clasping hands together to represent unity, collaboration, or a strong bond.
- d. Tapping fingers on a surface to metaphorically express impatience or anticipation.

4. Beat

Beat gestures refer to movements or facial expressions that are synchronized with the rhythm or beat of music or dance. In the context of dance, beat gestures include movements performed by dancers with respect to a clear musical beat. This means that the dance movements are directed and shown on each beat of the music or in a structured rhythmic pattern.

Examples:

- a. Clapping hands rhythmically to emphasize a point or celebrate success.
- b. Tapping fingers on a table in sync with speech to mark key points in a narrative.
- c. Using hand movements to create a rhythmic flow during storytelling or public speaking.
- d. Alternating hand movements with speech to maintain engagement and pacing in communication.

Meaning Gestures

Raah (2015) emphasizes that gestures are a form of non-verbal communication, expressing intentions, emotions, or thoughts. Different movements have specific meanings:

- a. Open palm wave means indicates farewell.
- b. Fist in face signals means threat or anger.
- c. Thumbs up means represents approval.
- d. Thumbs down means rejection or a problem.
- e. Clapping demonstrates means appreciation or happiness.
- f. Hand behind head means reflects high confidence and self-assurance.

Cultural differences influence how hand motions are interpreted; for example, palms facing down may suggest a commanding "Stop now" or a reassuring "Calm down." Understanding the context is crucial; a pointing finger may mean immediate action. To interpret gestures accurately, one must consider both cultural nuances and the specific situation.

Semantic Meaning

Semantic meaning in language pertains to how words or language signals convey ideas and importance. This facet of language analysis delves into the connection between linguistic elements and the concepts they represent. Chaer (1994) categorizes semantic meaning into three key elements:

1. Lexical Meaning

Lexical meaning pertains to a word's inherent meaning, both in its basic form and as a derivative lexeme, and this meaning is well-established, as found in a dictionary. For instance, the term "eyes" carries the lexical meaning of the organs or senses in the head that enable sight. The lexical meaning of a word is self-contained when the term stands alone. However, if a word is part of a phrase, its meaning might change. Therefore, there are words whose lexical meaning becomes evident only when they are connected to other terms.

2. Grammatical Meaning

Grammatical meaning is derived from grammatical processes such as reduplication, word compounding, or affixation. Using the example of "eyes," it initially carries the lexical meaning related to the organs or senses for seeing. Yet, when used in the context of a sentence like "Hi, where are your eyes?" it no longer refers to the instruments for seeing but takes on a grammatical meaning related to style or a negative outcome.

3. Contextual Meaning

Contextual meaning is determined by the relationship between a word's meaning in context and the situation in which it is used. For instance, if a child accidentally breaks a glass, and the mother exclaims, "How clever you are," the praise in this context is negative because the mother is upset with her child.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilizes qualitative research to investigate the intricate aspects of traditional Indonesian dance gestures and meanings when welcoming guests. Employing various data sources, the researcher analyzes and explains the details, aiming to offer a profound understanding of the subject and contribute to generating hypotheses and new theories for further research. This research uses data where the data uses 10 regional dance videos originating from Aceh, Jambi, Riau, West Sumatra, South Sulawesi, Papua, East Nusa Tenggara, Jakarta, Central Java, and North Sumatra, researchers use this video as a source material for research and analysis of this theory (Charles Sanders Peirce, 1857-1914), and involved an analysis of dance movements, first considering their contextual meaning and then delving deeper into an examination based on theories related to the types of gestures or movements that been showcase includes iconic, deictic, metaphoric, and Beat. The researchers found 50 data from the 10 dance videos based on gestures or movements, including iconic, deictic, metaphoric, and beat.

RESULTS

No	Gestures	Amount	Percentage
1	Iconic	24	48%
2	Deictic	6	12%
3	Metaphoric	16	32%
4	Beat	4	8%
	TOTAL	50	100%

DISCUSSION

1. Iconic

A. Sekapur Sirih (Jambi)

Figure 2. Sekapur Sirih (Jambi)

Lyrics: "Sajian iko darilah jambi, Sepucuk jambi sembilan lurah, Sajian kami pusako mulyo, Adatlah resam dari dulu kalo" ("This offering is from Jambi, a

piece of Jambi with nine districts, Our offering is a precious heritage. Tradition has been the custom since ancient times.")

Sekapur Sirih dance is a dance originating from Indonesia and is a regional dance of Jambi. This dance is a guest welcoming dance which is usually danced by female dancers. This dance illustrates harmony, purity, and togetherness in the culture of the people of South Sumatra. However, sekapur sirih dance is also often performed in traditional events, such as weddings, engagements, or religious events in South Sumatra, Indonesia. In addition, this dance is also often part of art and cultural performances, where dance artists perform the beauty of movements and symbolic meanings on stage. From the picture can be seen the female dancers bowing and putting their hands together, and looking forward. There is also a box right in front of one of the women, this tells us that they respect the guests who come, symbolizing harmony, and purity. This movement is an iconic, where iconic gestures refer to the use of body movements or facial expressions that have a specific meaning and can be understood visually, similar to what the icon or symbol represents. That is because this movement provides a symbol, namely with both hands put together, then kowtow, this is a symbol of respect for guests who come, a symbol of harmony and purity that comes from Jambi.

b. Zapin (Riau)

Figure 3. Zapin (Riau)

Lyrics: "Menari menarilah tarian Melayu, Menari menarilah jangan rasa malu, Menari menarilah sejujur hatimu, Menari menarilah tanpa rasa jemu" ("Dance, dance the Malay dance, Dance, dance without feeling ashamed, Dance, dance with all your honesty, Dance, dance without feeling weary.")

Zapin dance is a dance originating from Indonesia, precisely from the Riau region. Zapin dance holds a deep meaning in every dance movement, such as reflecting the cultural wealth, history, and identity of the Malay people. Zapin is often performed in various events such as celebrations, traditional ceremonies, or religious events. The movements in this dance often depict daily life, togetherness, as well as religious and social values. Zapin dance was originally born from the form of foot games played by Arab and Persian men. From the picture can be seen the movement of the outstretched hand facing forward with the body facing to the side, this means that the dancer invites the invitees to join the event. This movement includes iconic movements, where iconic gestures are a form of non-verbal communication that uses body movements and provides

symbols to convey certain meanings, That is because, the movement gives symbols and meanings. with hands extended forward and the body facing to the side, this movement means, which is where the dancer invites the audience to join the event.

2. Deictic

A. Dana-Dana Caca (Gorontalo)

Figure 4. Dana-Dana Caca (Gorontalo)

Lyrics: "mora kahi dana dana, wow..... caca" ("Like spreading grains, wow... laughter.")

Dana-dana caca dance is an Indonesian folk dance originating from the Gorontalo region. This dance is a regional dance to welcome guests to an event, but dana dana caca dance is also used as an expression of gratitude and happiness. dana dana caca dance has unique and interesting dance movements. From the picture, it can be seen that the dancers bowed their bodies and spread their hands forward, meaning that they welcomed and respected the guests who came. This dance is included in the deictic, where, deictic gestures are a form of non-verbal communication that uses gestures or body movements to point or refer directly to a specific object or person in the context of communication. That is because this dance refers or points to the guests and provides communication without using words, namely with the movement of the dancers bending the body and stretching both hands forward this gives the meaning that the dancer welcomes the guests but indirectly he says welcome through the movements that refer to the guests.

B. Kipas Pakarena (South Sulawesi)

Figure 5. Kipas Pakarena (South Sulawesi)

Lyric: "Ikatte ri turatea, bau/daeng, Adatta marioloa, sayang, E Aule, Pakarenayya, Pakarenayya La'biri' ri pa'gaukang" ("We are the people of the top (Makassar tribe), Having customs held since long ago, dear, Oh my, the dances, Her dances are graceful in every performance.")

Pakarena fan dance is a regional dance originating from Indonesia, precisely from South Sulawesi, this dance has the characteristic of using a fan in dancing. This dance illustrates the beauty of the movements and harmony of the dancers. Hand movements with fans symbolize grace and gentleness, while body movements express joy and harmony. Pakarena Fan Dance is often performed in cultural events, traditional ceremonies, religious celebrations, welcoming guests, and art festivals in South Sulawesi. From the picture can be seen the dancers using fans and waving them and hands spread out this symbolizes joy, revival and tenderness, this is the main and unique feature of the dance, using fans. This dance movement includes deictic gestures where, Deictic gestures are a form of non-verbal communication that uses gestures or body movements to point or refer directly to a specific object or person in the context of communication. That is because this movement refers to the guests and provides communication in addition to words, or nonverbal communication, where the dancers raise one hand while waving a fan, the other hand is placed in front of the chest and the head is facing to the side, which indirectly this movement conveys their excitement over the arrival of the guests without using words.

3. Metaphoric

A. Yamko Rambe Yamko (Papua)

Figure 6. Yamko Rambe Yamko (Papua)

Lyrics: "Hee yamko rambe yamko aronawa kombe, Teemi nokibe kubano ko bombe ko, Yuma no bungo awe ade" ("Hee yamko rambe yamko, the unity is our foundation We stand together, strong and firm for the glory of our land and people.")

Yamko Rambe Yamko dance is an Indonesian regional dance originating from the Papua region. Yamko Rambe Yamko dance is a dance that has fast music. This dance depicts the joy and spirit of life of the Papuan people. This dance is usually often performed in various cultural events and celebrations in Papua, such as cultural festivals, traditional ceremonies, commemoration of holidays, welcoming guests, and other cultural events. From the picture it can be seen that the dancers are so serious and focused in dancing, by looking forward, this illustrates and means that the dancers are serious and focused. This dance movement includes metaphoric gestures. Where, metaphoric gesture is a form of non-verbal communication that uses facial expressions to convey meaning symbolically or metaphorically, not directly related to the object or concept being discussed. because this movement displays the facial expressions or expressions of the dancers that give meaning, in the yamko Rambe yamko dance movement the facial expressions of the dancers are so serious and this focus gives the meaning that the spirit of life of the Papuan people.

B. Caci (East Nusa Tenggara)

Figure 7. Caci (East Nusa Tenggara)

Lyrics: "naraga, naraga.....,naraga.....,ngalis dia na me rantang pau ngali "
("Naraga, naraga, naraga, he/she looks for a reason while I continue to wander aimlessly.")

Caci dance is a dance originating from Indonesia, precisely from the Flores region, East Nusa Tenggara Province. This dance depicts a battle between two people using caci, which is a shield covered with leather and rattan, as well as its completeness, caci dance means the values of courage, honesty, and solidarity in the face of conflict. Caci Dance is usually performed in various cultural events and traditional ceremonies in Manggarai, Flores. Events such as cultural festivals, traditional wedding ceremonies, or special celebrations often feature Caci Dance. From the picture can be seen that a man is very serious, this illustrates courage and victory in battle. Caci dance is usually performed by male dancers, because the dance means war. This dance movement includes metaporic gestures. Where, metaporic gesture is a form of non-verbal communication that uses facial expressions to convey meaning symbolically or metaphorically, not directly related to the object or concept being discussed. That is because this movement shows a serious facial expression or facial exorcism, in the dance movement there is someone who is so serious and focused which in the Flores tribe means courage and courage.

4. Beat

A. Campak (Jakarta)

Figure 8. Campak (Jakarta)

Lyrics: "Empat empat punai sekawan, Hanyalah satu berbulu kaki, Empat-empat miak sekawan, Hanyalah satu setuyju hati" ("Four four doves in harmony, Only one with feathered feet. Four four meowing friends, Only one in agreement of heart.")

Campak dance is a regional dance originating from Indonesia, precisely from Bangka Belitung. Campak dance depicts the joy and spirit of mutual cooperation in society. The movements in Measles Dance reflect the cohesiveness and togetherness between dancers. Campak dance is usually performed in various traditional events, such as religious celebrations, cultural festivals, weddings, welcoming guests or special events that commemorate important moments. From the picture it can be seen that the dancer stomps his feet together, while looking forward, this is a symbol of joy, the stomping of the feet means a blazing spirit. That's why this movement is a beat gesture. Where, beat gesture,

in contexts commonly associated with music or the performing arts, refers to body movements or facial expressions that are orchestrated or synchronized precisely with the rhythm or beat of an artwork. That is because the dancer gives a foot tapping motion that symbolizes a burning spirit.

B. Topeng Ireng (Central Java)

Figure 9. Topeng Ireng (Central Java)

Lyrics: " Sekecakno Anggenipun Lenggah Iro", "Sinambi Mrekso Rupo Engkang Mboten Toto" ("Reveal the purpose of the dance, my friend", "Simultaneously, consider what is not yet clear.")

Topeng ireng dance is a dance originating from Indonesia, precisely from Tuksono Village, Borobudur District, Magelang Regency, Central Java. This dance is unique in that the crown used is made of feather decoration with a large size. Topeng Ireng Dance depicts everyday life, joy, and courage. The movements in this dance often depict the characters of heroes or figures in Javanese mythology. Topeng Ireng dance is usually performed in various traditional events such as traditional ceremonies, cultural festivals, religious celebrations, and art performances. From the picture can be seen there are several dancers stomping us which means courage, peace, and joy. This dance movement is included in the beat gesture. Wherebeat gesture, in contexts commonly associated with music or the performing arts, refers to body movements or facial expressions that are orchestrated or synchronized precisely with the rhythm or beat of an artwork. That is because the movement features waving hands and shrugging shoulders following the accompaniment of this music means courage and courage.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Figure 10. Percentage

This research aims into the profound meanings embedded in the gestures and movements of traditional Indonesian dances, specifically those performed to welcome guests. The study categorizes the movements into iconic, deictic, metaphoric, and beat gestures, revealing the rich cultural tapestry woven into these expressions. The results of the analysis, based on 10 regional dance videos from various Indonesian provinces, showcase a predominant presence of iconic gestures, constituting 48% of the total movements. These iconic movements, such as hand gestures symbolizing respect and harmony, play a crucial role in conveying cultural values and stories associated with each dance.

Additionally, deictic gestures, representing 12% of the total movements, focus on directly pointing or referring to specific objects or persons, subtly communicating messages of welcome and gratitude. Metaphoric gestures, comprising 32% of the movements, involve using movements or facial expressions to convey metaphorical or symbolic meanings, adding layers of depth to the narrative of the dances. Lastly, beat gestures, accounting for 8%, synchronize movements with the rhythm or beat of the music, amplifying the emotional impact of the performances. As Indonesia grapples with the challenge of preserving its traditional dances in the face of waning interest among the younger generation, this research serves as a vital resource in fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation for the intricate gestures that encapsulate the cultural identity of the nation.

From the results of the analysis, the gesture that we encountered the most from the dance was iconic and the least was the beat gesture because in Indonesian regional dance, on average, it uses relaxed music and prioritizes the symbol of the movement and the symbol, while in the beat gesture it uses faster music and usually beat gestures are found more in Indonesian regional dance from Papua, because Papuan music has a fast music flow. and more iconic gestures than beats due to the diversity of cultures in Indonesia. Each dance often reflects a tradition, a story or a symbolic meaning, so iconic gestures become a means of conveying that message.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Gesture and Their Meaning of Artistic Movements in Welcoming Guest in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

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